

Curvature and Bottlenecks Control Molecular Transport in Inverse Bicontinuous Cubic Phases

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We perform a simulation study of the diffusion of small solutes in the confined domains imposed by inverse bicontinuous cubic phases for the primitive, diamond and gyroid symmetries common to many lipid/water mesophase systems employed in experiments. For large diffusing domains, the long-time diffusion coefficient shows universal features when the size of the confining domain is renormalized by the Gaussian curvature of the triply-periodic minimal surface. When bottlenecks are widely present, they become the most relevant factor for transport, regardless of the connectivity of the cubic phase.

I. INTRODUCTION

Inverse Bicontinuous Cubic Phases (IBCPs) are nanoscopic lipidic aggregates employed in several biotechnological applications, such as membrane proteins crystallization, ion pumps, materials design, complex food systems and controlled drug delivery¹⁻⁵, and have been observed in several instances *in vivo*⁶⁻⁸. At the microscopic scale, these aggregates show a periodic structure, where a single lipid bilayer encompasses the whole system and partitions the space filled by water into two interpenetrating, noncommunicating periodic networks of channels characterized by regular lattices with coordination number q . The midplane of the lipid bilayer (corresponding to the lipid tails) lies on a Triply-Periodic Minimal Surface (TPMS), where the local mean curvature is zero at each point^{9,10}. The geometrical and topological properties of IBCPs can be closely controlled by tuning temperature or lipid concentration, or by adding suitable cosurfactants¹¹⁻¹⁷. The TPMSs usually observed in experiments show the primitive, diamond and gyroid symmetries^{11-13,15}, corresponding to the $\text{Im}\bar{3}\text{m}$, $\text{Pn}\bar{3}\text{m}$ and $\text{Ia}\bar{3}\text{d}$ space groups (the associated lattices have $q = 6, 4, 3$, see Fig.1).

In view of the many applications in drug-delivery nanotechnology, molecular transport through IBCPs has been the focus of intense experimental efforts^{15,18-29}. These works have unveiled a heterogeneous palette of delivery performances, depending on factors such as the symmetry of the cubic phase^{15,20,24}, the size of the diffusion domains as well as the relative amount of water used in the production of the IBCP^{15,25,28}; or the nature (hydrophilic vs hydrophobic) of the diffusing molecules^{19,24}. Unfortunately, it is not an easy task to experimentally address the role played by each of these features. For example, for a given lipid the $\text{Im}\bar{3}\text{m}$ phase is typically obtained by adding a cosurfactant, and larger amounts of water and wider channels are observed with respect to the $\text{Pn}\bar{3}\text{m}$ symmetry¹⁵. Although the experiments point

FIG. 1. Top: Repeating units of the three symmetries considered. The lipid bilayer is depicted in orange, while one of the networks of water channels is represented in cyan. Bottom: Corresponding regular lattices.

towards a larger diffusivity of hydrophilic molecules for $\text{Im}\bar{3}\text{m}$ ¹⁵, it is not clear whether this result is due to the higher coordination number, the increased hydration of the system or the specific geometrical properties of the two phases.

A better insight into this aspect can be obtained by theoretical considerations. In this regard, in spite of the vast literature dealing with the diffusion of confined particles (see *e.g.*³⁰⁻⁴⁴), only a few works have focused on IBCPs. The effect of connectivity and available volume on the diffusion of a particle within the $\text{Im}\bar{3}\text{m}$ and $\text{Pn}\bar{3}\text{m}$ phases has been explored numerically by means of the cell model³², although no clear link to the basic geometrical properties of the IBCPs was reported. Moreover, the surface diffusion on the water-lipid interface has been studied both semi-analytically³² and by means of simulations^{45,46}.

In this work, we tackle the problem by means of Brownian Dynamics simulations, and directly relate the long-time diffusive behavior of particles within IBCPs to their

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FIG. 2. Schematic picture of the definition of the signed distance d (top). Moving the minimal surface parallelly to itself, one can obtain shrunk (bottom left) or swollen channels (bottom right). In the bottom panels, the diffusion domain is depicted in cyan.

geometrical properties. For wide channels, the long-time diffusion coefficient is shown to be determined by the average Gaussian curvature independently of the symmetry considered. Conversely, the large heterogeneity of the local radius present in narrow channels induces a symmetry-dependent reduction of the diffusion speed, due to the presence of bottlenecks. By analyzing available experimental data in light of our results, we then estimate the amount of water molecules bound to lipid heads present in real systems, in good agreement with direct observations.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For any point P in space, we can define the *signed distance* d from the minimal surface. The magnitude of d gives the distance separating P from the closest point belonging to the minimal surface, while its sign indicates which of the half spaces identified by the TPMS contains P (Fig.2 top). For a hydrophilic particle, the diffusion domain is identified by the set of points for which $d > l$, and by tuning l the level of confinement can be controlled (Fig.2 bottom). In this regard, we note that the TPMS partitions space into two equivalent regions, corresponding to $d > 0$ and $d < 0$, which we name \mathcal{R}_+ and \mathcal{R}_- . Within our convention on signs, for $l = 0$ the diffusion domain is identified by \mathcal{R}_+ . When $l \neq 0$, the boundary surface is identified by parallelly-moving the TPMS by a distance $|l|$ towards the domain corresponding to the

sign of l (Fig.2 bottom). Due to the equivalence of the two regions identified by the TPMS, the features of the boundary surface are dependent only on the magnitude of l . The sign serves to identify the diffusion domain via the condition $d > l$. If $l > 0$, the domain is obtained as the set of points belonging to \mathcal{R}_+ and having a distance from the TPMS larger than $|l|$, thus obtaining a shrunk channel (Fig.2 bottom-left). If $l < 0$, the condition $d > l$ implies that the diffusion domain includes the whole region \mathcal{R}_+ and the set of points belonging to \mathcal{R}_- and having a distance from the TPMS smaller than $|l|$. In this way, a swollen channel is obtained (Fig.2 bottom-right). The systems of direct relevance for experiments are those where $l > 0$, in which case l corresponds to the length of a lipid within the bilayer (one can account for the finite size of particles by including also their radius in l). We will nevertheless also consider $l < 0$, as it helps providing a complete picture of the transport properties of IBCPs. Finally, the diffusion of a hydrophobic particle within the lipid bilayer can be described by considering the domain defined by $|d| < l$, with $l > 0$.

In our computations, the diffusive motion was simulated according to Brownian Dynamics (BD) combined with Monte Carlo (MC) moves⁴⁷, while the TPMSs were implemented via their approximations as nodal surfaces⁴⁸ (see Appendix for simulation details). We performed for each IBCP a systematic set of simulations encompassing the whole range of possible values of l . The latter was identified by considering only the values $|l| < l_c$ not leading to a self-overlapping boundary, where l_c is a symmetry-dependent critical value. For $l > l_c$, different parts of the confining wall come into contact and the channels cannot percolate the whole system, so that the particle is trapped in the neighborhood of its initial position. Conversely, overly-swollen channels ($l < -l_c$) lead to a nonpercolating wall: The confinement is now induced by a set of small, isolated obstacles, a system which has already been extensively studied^{31,36,49} and is not the focus of the present work.

To study the diffusion speed, we focused on the Mean-Square Displacement $MSD(t) \equiv \langle (\mathbf{r}(t) - \mathbf{r}(0))^2 \rangle$, where $\mathbf{r}(t)$ is the position of the diffusing particle at time t and the angle brackets denote statistical average. Examples of the typical evolution of $MSD(t)$ are reported in Fig.3. At short times, the particle diffuses locally, barely interacting with the walls, and $MSD(t) \simeq 6D_0t$, where D_0 is the diffusion coefficient in the absence of confinement (continuous line). At long times, scales larger than the lattice parameter a of the cubic phase are explored by the random motion, and the IBCP can be regarded to as a homogeneous system characterized by an effective diffusion coefficient $D < D_0$ (dashed lines). These two regimes are separated by a transition region with subdiffusive dynamics.

We characterized the transport properties of the system by the value of D obtained by fitting the long-time kinetics of the mean-square displacement (Fig.3). The level of confinement corresponding to a certain value of

FIG. 3. Evolution of $MSD(t)$ for three representative cases with $Im\bar{3}m$ symmetry with $l = 0$ (stars), $l = 0.165$ (circles) and $l = 0.21$ (squares). The corresponding unit cells are sketched as insets. Here and in all the subsequent figures, error bars are not reported as they are always smaller than the size of symbols.

l can be captured by considering the volume fraction ϕ occupied by the diffusion domain. According to whether diffusion is taking place inside the lipid bilayer or in one of the water channels, one has $\phi = \phi_{mem}$ or $\phi = \phi_{chan}$, respectively. By Steiner's formula

$$\phi_{mem} = 2A_0 \frac{l}{a} + \frac{4}{3}\pi\chi \left(\frac{l}{a}\right)^3 \quad (1)$$

for the membrane domains and

$$\phi_{chan} = \frac{1 - \phi_{mem}}{2} = \frac{1 - 2A_0 \frac{l}{a} - \frac{4}{3}\pi\chi \left(\frac{l}{a}\right)^3}{2} \quad (2)$$

for diffusion within water channels, where A_0 is the area of the TPMS per unit cell normalized by a^2 , while χ is its Euler-Poincaré characteristic¹³. For $Im\bar{3}m$, $Pn\bar{3}m$ and $Ia\bar{3}d$ these quantities read $A_0 \simeq 2.345, 1.919, 3.091$ and $\chi = -4, -2, -8$ respectively¹³. Alternatively, the level of confinement can be addressed by considering the normalized quantity $l\sqrt{-K_0}$, where

$$K_0 = \frac{2\pi\chi}{A_0 a^2} \quad (3)$$

is the average Gaussian curvature of the TPMS. For a system with lipids of length l ,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{-K_0}} = l + r, \quad (4)$$

where r is the average radius of water channels¹¹. For membrane diffusion, the quantity $l\sqrt{-K_0}$ is thus the thickness of the bilayer divided by its theoretical maximum value (due to the inhomogeneities of IBCPs, this

is actually an upper bound). Analogously, due to the possibility of swelling the maximum radius of channels is $r_{max} \equiv 2/\sqrt{-K_0}$ (corresponding to $l = -1/\sqrt{-K_0}$ in Eq.(4)), thus

$$l\sqrt{-K_0} = 1 - 2\frac{r}{r_{max}} \quad (5)$$

can be interpreted as a measure of the level of confinement of the diffusing particle.

A. Diffusion within the membrane bilayer

In Fig.4 we report the results for D/D_0 for diffusion of a particle within the domain corresponding to the lipid bilayer. Remarkably, membrane transport shows universal features when D/D_0 is plotted as a function of $l\sqrt{-K_0}$ (Fig.4). In this case, the diffusion volume is bounded by parallel confining walls, and the transport is highly efficient, with D/D_0 ranging from $2/3$ (two-dimensional diffusion over the TPMS³², attained for $l \rightarrow 0$) to 1 . This universality indicates that, for parallel boundaries, diffusion is a function of the thickness of the bilayer normalized by its maximum theoretical value, independently of the details of the TPMS.

FIG. 4. D/D_0 for a hydrophobic particle as a function of $l\sqrt{-K_0}$ (main plot) and ϕ_{mem} (inset).

In the inset of Fig.4 the same data are shown as a function of ϕ_{mem} , as defined by Eq.(1). In this case, the data still roughly follow a master curve, although a systematic deviation can be observed for large values of ϕ_{mem} . This is readily understood by some algebraic arguments. From Eq.(3), one can write

$$\frac{l}{a} = \frac{l}{a} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{-K_0}}{\sqrt{-K_0}} = \sqrt{-\frac{A_0}{2\pi\chi}} \cdot l\sqrt{-K_0}, \quad (6)$$

so that Eq.(1) can be rewritten as

$$\phi_{mem} = 2A_0 \sqrt{-\frac{A_0}{2\pi\chi}} \left[l\sqrt{-K_0} - \frac{1}{3} \left(l\sqrt{-K_0} \right)^3 \right]. \quad (7)$$

Let us define

$$\bar{\phi}_{mem} \equiv \frac{\phi_{mem}}{2A_0 \sqrt{-\frac{A_0}{2\pi\chi}}} = l\sqrt{-K_0} - \frac{1}{3} \left(l\sqrt{-K_0} \right)^3. \quad (8)$$

The details of the specific IBCP considered appear in the formula defining $\bar{\phi}_{mem}$ only in the combination $l\sqrt{-K_0}$, thus the universality observed in the main plot in Fig.4 would be maintained if one were to report D/D_0 as a function of $\bar{\phi}_{mem}$. As for the variable ϕ_{mem} , a numerical check shows that $2A_0 \sqrt{-\frac{A_0}{2\pi\chi}}$ holds similar yet not equal values for the three IBCPs (0.72,0.75,0.77 for Im $\bar{3}m$, Pn $\bar{3}m$, Ia $\bar{3}d$ respectively), which explains the reason behind the ‘‘almost’’ collapsed data in the inset of Fig.4.

B. Diffusion within water channels

In the case of diffusion within the water channels, a more complex scenario emerges from the simulations. For large diffusion domains, the data follow a master curve when plotted as a function of $l\sqrt{-K_0}$ (Fig.5 top). As this result can be rephrased in terms of r/r_{max} by Eq.(5), we can conclude that also in this case diffusion is determined by the size of channels normalized by their maximum theoretical value. This universality is not limited to the present class of systems. For example, an alternative model for experimental IBCPs assumes Constant Mean Curvature (CMC) rather than uniform bilayer thickness⁵⁰. When systems with CMC boundaries are considered, the simulation data for D/D_0 fall again onto the same master curve as in the case of parallel confining walls, as we report in Fig.5 bottom, unveiling the presence of a universal mechanism independent of the geometrical details of the IBCPs.

For smaller channels, the curves corresponding to different symmetries depart from each other. This difference cannot be simply ascribed to the connectivity of the IBCPs, as the transport performance is not ordered according to their coordination numbers. Quite the opposite, Im $\bar{3}m$ ($q = 6$) shows the slowest diffusion behavior, while the best result is achieved by Ia $\bar{3}d$ ($q = 3$). Pure connectivity is actually irrelevant to determine the value of D . This fact was observed numerically by considering the Interconnected-Rod (IR) model, where the same topology is maintained but the water channels have a constant radius³² (this can be achieved by uniformly inflating the rods in Fig.1). Here, we analyze the role of connectivity by considering the IR model in the limit of infinitely-thin channels. This corresponds to a Random Walk (RW) over the lattice associated with the IBCP.

FIG. 5. D/D_0 for a hydrophilic particle as a function of $l\sqrt{-K_0}$ for parallel confining walls (top) and constant mean-curvature boundaries (bottom). The continuous line in the bottom panel highlights the master curve obtained from the data in the top panel.

As this one-dimensional RW is embedded in a three-dimensional space, the diffusion coefficient is damped by a factor of three, $D/D_0 = 1/3$. Indeed, let \mathbf{u}_i be the vector corresponding to the i -th step of the RW. Due to the isotropy of the lattice, the length of this vector is $|\mathbf{u}_i| = \sqrt{\mu}a \equiv \sigma$ independently of i . The value of μ is the square of the length of one lattice step normalized by a , and can be computed with the aid of Fig.1 bottom. For Im $\bar{3}m$, two neighbor lattice nodes are located at the centers of two consecutive cell units, thus $\mu = 1$ in this case. For Pn $\bar{3}m$, the neighbors are located at the center and at a corner of a repeating unit, with coordinates (for $a = 1$) equal to e.g. $(0, 0, 0)$ and $(1/2, 1/2, 1/2)$ respectively. For this symmetry, one thus has $\mu = 3 \cdot (1/2)^2 = 3/4$. The case of Ia $\bar{3}d$ is more cumbersome, but it can be shown that⁵¹ $\mu = 1/8$. Let us denote the typical time needed

for a step of the RW as τ . Assuming the RW to start at the origin ($\mathbf{r}(0) = 0$), the position after N steps (corresponding to a time $t = N\tau$) is $\mathbf{r}(N\tau) = \sum_i \mathbf{u}_i$. The various steps are independent identically-distributed random variables with variance equal to σ^2 . Due to the Central Limit Theorem, for $N \gg 1$ the random variable $\mathbf{r}(N\tau)$ is distributed according to a Gaussian with variance $N\sigma^2$, i.e. $MSD(N\tau) = \langle \mathbf{r}(N\tau)^2 \rangle = N\sigma^2$. Since by definition $MSD(N\tau) = 6D \cdot N\tau$, one finally finds

$$D = \frac{\sigma^2}{6\tau} = \frac{\mu a^2}{6\tau}. \quad (9)$$

The typical jump time can be easily estimated as $\tau = \sigma^2/(2D_0)$, since each step is characterized by one-dimensional diffusion. Substitution into Eq.(9) thus yields $D/D_0 = 1/3$ independently of the symmetry considered. This limiting analytic computation is in agreement with the numerical results reported in Ref.³².

C. Diffusion close to the percolation threshold

The reduced symmetry-dependent performance in the transport properties can be ascribed to the presence of bottlenecks. This feature has been reported for disordered systems, where the exponent for the conductivity close to the percolation threshold strongly depends on the stochastic mechanism controlling the reduction of available space⁵². IBCPs are in this context rather unique structures, as they show percolation in spite of having no randomness. As soon as $l > l_c$ the lipid bilayer overlaps with itself and D drops to zero. This self-intersection does not take place uniformly, so that close to the percolation threshold the local radius of the channels is highly heterogeneous (see for instance the sketches in Fig.3). The event of a particle passing through a bottleneck is highly unfavourable from an entropic perspective, and its trajectory shows the typical features of hopping kinetics (Fig.6), where the position fluctuates for a long time around a constant value (i.e. it is trapped in a cage) and then suddenly jumps to a new point (i.e. it passes through a bottleneck).

The presence of bottlenecks is best evaluated by considering ϕ_{chan} as independent variable (Fig.7 top). Note that the amount of water ϕ_{wat} used to prepare the IBCP in typical experiments is equal to $\phi_{wat} = 2\phi_{chan}$. A swollen IBCP ($l < 0$) has $\phi_{chan} > 1/2$, which is consistent with the fact that this case is not compatible with the construction of an IBCP with congruent channels. This change of variable does not affect the qualitative features of the results, although it perturbs the collapse of data for swollen channels for analogous reasons as in the case of diffusion within the lipid bilayer. At the percolation threshold, D drops to zero, since the cages are disconnected from each other. The corresponding critical volume ϕ_{chan}^c highlights how differently the IBCPs optimize their inner space for transport, with a 40-fold difference between Im $\bar{3}m$ and Ia $\bar{3}d$ (inset in Fig.7 top).

FIG. 6. Example of hopping kinetics close to the percolation threshold for a particle diffusing in the water channels of an Im $\bar{3}m$ with $l/a = 0.2274$, corresponding to $l\sqrt{-K_0} \simeq 0.746$ and $\phi_{chan} \simeq 0.065$.

These results also hold for CMC boundaries, although the quantitative details are system-dependent (Fig.7 bottom).

This picture is confirmed by directly computing the variance of the local radius normalized by the square of the average radius, $\Delta r^2/r^2$. Let us first focus on the TPMSs, for which $r = 1/\sqrt{-K_0} \equiv r_0$. The variance can be computed by considering a mesh on the minimal surface and calculating for each point its distance from the medial surface, which gives an estimation of the local radius⁵³. A numerical inspection gives $\Delta r^2/r_0^2 \simeq 0.0267, 0.0075, 0.0021$ for Im $\bar{3}m$, Pn $\bar{3}m$ and Ia $\bar{3}d$, respectively. For a narrow channel, the local value of the radius is obtained by shifting the corresponding TPMS radius by the constant quantity l . It is easy to check that the variance Δr^2 does not change under a constant shift. As a consequence, the relative ratio $\Delta r^2/r^2$ for any IBCP can be easily obtained by suitably rescaling the results found for the TPMSs, and the relative ratios between the values obtained for the three TPMSs are maintained at all levels of confinement if one compares IBCPs corresponding to the same value of $r\sqrt{-K_0}$. Therefore, the values of $\Delta r^2/r^2$ are in the ratios 12.7 : 3.6 : 1 for Im $\bar{3}m$, Pn $\bar{3}m$ and Ia $\bar{3}d$ cubic phases with water channels of equal normalized radius $r\sqrt{-K_0}$, indicating a significant difference in heterogeneity of channels sizes in the three IBCPs, in line with the results reported in Fig.7.

Quantitatively, the effective diffusion coefficient resulting from the hopping dynamics close to the percolation threshold is still described by Eq.(9), although now τ depends on the geometrical details of cages and bottlenecks. Adapting the theory by Berezhkovskii et al. to the present context³⁷, we approximate the bottlenecks as thin effective cylinders of length L and radius $\rho \equiv l_c - l$

FIG. 7. Top: D/D_0 for a hydrophilic particle as a function of ϕ_{chan} for parallel confining walls, together with the best fit according to Eq.(11). Bottom: D/D_0 vs ϕ_{chan} for constant mean-curvature boundaries.

(within the present choice of variables $l = l(\phi_{chan})$ and $l_c \equiv l(\phi_{chan}^c)$). The average time τ corresponds to the typical time needed for a successful jump to the next cage. In order to perform a jump, the particle needs to find the entrance of a bottleneck, for which it needs a typical searching time τ_s . Once inside the cylinder, the diffusing particle has still to cross it, spending on average a time \bar{t} to do so. In order to get the total jumping time τ , one has to sum these two contributions, and normalize by the translocation probability P_{tr} :

$$\tau = \frac{\tau_s + \bar{t}}{P_{tr}}. \quad (10)$$

Following Ref.³⁷, we estimate the various terms as $\bar{t} = \pi\rho L/(8D_0)$, $P_{tr} = 1/[2 + 4L/(\pi\rho)]$ and $\tau_s = V_c/(4D_0\rho q)$, where $V_c = a^3\phi_{chan}$ is the volume of the cage. The rigorous derivation of these formulas assumes spherical cages

connected by thin, perfectly-straight cylinders. The application to the present case serves thus as an approximation, although it provides key insights into the impact of bottlenecks on diffusion, as we show below. Plugging these expressions into Eq.(10) and making use of Eq.(9), we finally obtain

$$\frac{D}{D_0} = \frac{2\pi q\mu a^2 \rho^2}{3(\pi\rho + 2L)(2a^3\phi_{chan} + \pi\rho^2 qL)} \quad (11)$$

for $\text{Im}\bar{3}\text{m}$ and $\text{Pn}\bar{3}\text{m}$. For $\text{Ia}\bar{3}\text{d}$ the same formula holds, but ϕ_{chan} has to be divided by 8, that is, the number of nodes in the lattice within a unit cell (see Fig.1). Eq.(11) satisfactorily fits the simulation data close to the threshold (continuous lines in the inset of Fig.7 top), where it can account for more than two orders of magnitude of values of D/D_0 . The best fits were obtained by tuning L and ϕ_{chan}^c , and correspond to $\phi_{chan}^c \simeq 0.056, 0.0081, 0.0012$ and $L/a \simeq 0.14, 0.09, 0.002$ for $\text{Im}\bar{3}\text{m}$, $\text{Pn}\bar{3}\text{m}$, $\text{Ia}\bar{3}\text{d}$ respectively. The optimizing values show again the correct ranking of the IBCPs, both for the homogeneity of channels (ϕ_{chan}^c) and the size of bottlenecks (L).

Eq.(11) further enables extracting the exponent regulating the diffusion coefficient in the vicinity of the percolation threshold. To this aim, we consider Eq.(11) in the limit $\rho \rightarrow 0$. To the leading order,

$$\frac{D}{D_0} \simeq \frac{\pi q\mu\rho^2}{6La\phi_{chan}^c} \propto \rho^2 = (l_c - l)^2. \quad (12)$$

Let us define the quantity $\epsilon \equiv \phi_{chan} - \phi_{chan}^c \ll 1$. Starting from Eq.(2) and noting that $\phi_{chan} = \phi_{chan}^c + \epsilon$ and $l = l_c - \rho$, we find

$$\phi_{chan}^c + \epsilon = \frac{1 - 2A_0\left(\frac{l_c - \rho}{a}\right) - \frac{4}{3}\pi\chi\left(\frac{l_c - \rho}{a}\right)^3}{2}. \quad (13)$$

Taylor-expanding with respect to ρ the right-hand-side of the previous formula and rearranging gives

$$\phi_{chan}^c + \epsilon \simeq \frac{1 - 2A_0\frac{l_c}{a} - \frac{4}{3}\pi\chi\left(\frac{l_c}{a}\right)^3}{2} + A_0\frac{\rho}{a} + 2\pi\chi\frac{l_c^2\rho}{a^3}, \quad (14)$$

where we dropped all the terms involving powers of ρ of order at least 2. The first term on the right-hand side in the previous formula gives ϕ_{chan}^c , so that at first order in ρ we can write

$$\epsilon \simeq \left(\frac{A_0}{a} + 2\pi\chi\frac{l_c^2}{a^3}\right)\rho \Rightarrow \rho \simeq \frac{\epsilon}{\frac{A_0}{a} + 2\pi\chi\frac{l_c^2}{a^3}}, \quad (15)$$

that is

$$l_c - l \simeq \frac{\phi_{chan} - \phi_{chan}^c}{\frac{A_0}{a} + 2\pi\chi\frac{l_c^2}{a^3}} \propto \phi_{chan} - \phi_{chan}^c. \quad (16)$$

Substitution into Eq.(12) finally yields $D \propto (\phi_{chan} - \phi_{chan}^c)^2$. This exponent, obtained for a periodic system, is interestingly in line with the results reported in literature for the conductivity in disordered systems, where the exponents typically lie in the range $1 - 4$ ^{49,54,55}.

D. Analysis of experimental data

When compared to experimental data, the theoretical results show a systematic overestimation of D/D_0 . Let us consider for instance the data reported in Ref.⁵⁶, where diffusion of glucose within a cubic phase with $Pn\bar{3}m$ symmetry was studied. The IBCP was produced by considering a mixture of water and monolinolein in weight proportions equal to $p_{wat} = 0.34$ and $1 - p_{wat} = 0.66$, respectively. The lattice parameter was $a = 85.8 \text{ \AA}$. The water volume fraction ϕ_{wat} can be computed as

$$\phi_{wat} = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{\rho_{wat}}{\rho_{lip}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_{wat}}\right)}, \quad (17)$$

where $\rho_{lip} = 1.05 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $\rho_{wat} = 1 \text{ g/cm}^3$ are respectively the density of the lipids and of water. In the present case we obtain $\phi_{wat} \simeq 0.35$, which is very close to p_{wat} due to the close proximity of the values of ρ_{lip} and ρ_{wat} . Now, $\phi_{chan} = \phi_{wat}/2 \simeq 0.175$, so that checking the data reported in Fig.7 top, we finally obtain a predicted value of the diffusion coefficient equal to $D/D_0 \simeq 0.47$. This is more than twice the experimental value reported in Ref.⁵⁶, where $D/D_0 \simeq 0.21$.

A possible reason for this discrepancy could be the finite size of glucose. Indeed, steric hindrance with the lipid bilayer effectively reduces the space available to diffusion of the center of mass. If we model the glucose molecule as a hard sphere of radius h , the closest point accessible to the center of mass is located at a distance $l + h$ from the TPMS. The value of h can be estimated as twice the hydrodynamic radius of glucose, i.e. by inverting the Stokes-Einstein equation:

$$h = \frac{k_B T}{6\pi\eta D_0} \simeq 3.2 \text{ \AA} \quad (18)$$

where $k_B T \simeq 4 \cdot 10^{-21} \text{ J}$ is the thermal energy, $\eta \simeq 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ the viscosity of water⁵⁷ and $D_0 \simeq 0.67 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ ⁵⁸. A direct inspection of the structure deposited on PubChem (PubChem CID: 5793) further shows that the maximum distance separating two atoms in the three dimensional structure is roughly $6.5 \text{ \AA} \simeq 2h$. Applying Eq.(2), one gets

$$1 - 2\phi_{chan} = 2A_0 \frac{l+h}{a} + \frac{4}{3}\pi\chi \left(\frac{l+h}{a}\right)^3, \quad (19)$$

For this system $l \simeq 16.4 \text{ \AA}$ can be obtained by inverting Eq.(1), where $\phi_{mem} = 1 - \phi_{wat} \simeq 0.65$. Substitution of $h \simeq 3.2 \text{ \AA}$ thus gives $\phi_{chan} \simeq 0.11$, resulting into $D/D_0 \simeq 0.41$ (compare Fig.7 top), which is only a small correction to the result for a point-like particle reported above. In order to obtain the experimental value $D/D_0 \simeq 0.21$, one would need $\phi_{chan} \simeq 0.025$. Inverting Eq.(19), we obtain the corresponding value $h \simeq 11 \text{ \AA}$, which is more than three times larger than the radius estimated in Eq.(18). While being relevant to some extent, the finite

size of glucose is thus not enough to explain the deviation of the experiments from the theoretical predictions.

A central role is instead expected to be played by the reduced mobility of water in proximity of the polar heads of the lipids. For example, in a water/monolein system tryptophane fluorescence experiments have identified two well-ordered layers of water molecules bound to the lipid heads followed by other two quasi-bound layers, with mobility properties halfway between bound and bulk molecules⁵⁹. This bound water can be assumed to diffuse at the same speed D_{lip} as the lipids in the bilayer. A simple way to take into account this feature is to consider the average between D_{lip} and the value predicted by the simulations, weighted according to x_b and $1 - x_b$ respectively, where x_b is the amount of bound water. As the value of D_{lip} is typically a couple of orders of magnitude lower than that of water²⁸, one can neglect the contributions from lipids and obtain

$$\left(\frac{D}{D_0}\right)_{exp} = (1 - x_b) \left(\frac{D}{D_0}\right)_{theory}. \quad (20)$$

To match experimental and theoretical results, one needs to set $x_b \simeq 0.55$.

In order to compute the thickness of the region corresponding to the bound water, we can make use of a modified version of Eq.(1). The total volume fraction corresponding to the bilayer and the bound water is equal to $(1 - \phi_{wat}) + x_b \phi_{wat}$ (remember that $\phi_{mem} = 1 - \phi_{wat}$). If w is the thickness of the region containing the bound water, one thus has

$$(1 - \phi_{wat}) + x_b \phi_{wat} = 2A_0 \frac{l+w}{a} + \frac{4}{3}\pi\chi \left(\frac{l+w}{a}\right)^3, \quad (21)$$

from which one can find the value of w . In the present case, we obtained $w \simeq 6.2 \text{ \AA}$, corresponding to roughly two layers of water molecules, in good agreement with the results on water mobility found in Ref.⁵⁹. Although water mobility is likely to have the largest impact on diffusion, it is worth noting that interactions between glucose and lipid heads may also play a role.

We repeated the same approach to analyze the data reported in Ref.²⁸, where the amino acid histidine diffuses in various mixtures of water and lipids. The bulk diffusion coefficient D_0 of histidine was estimated to be equal to $0.73 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$, assuming a room temperature equal to $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ⁶⁰. Also for this system the finite size of histidine does not explain the systematic overestimation of the diffusion coefficient (one would need a radius equal to roughly 16 \AA , to be compared to $h \simeq 3.1 \text{ \AA}$ as obtained from the Stokes-Einstein equation). Ascribing the discrepancy to the presence of bound water, values of w between 8 and 12 \AA were found, suggesting the presence of two to four layers of almost immobilized water. In Table I we report the numerical results.

We note that, assuming that w is always in the range found in the present section (two to four layers, i.e. 6 to 12 \AA), Eq. (21) can be employed to compute the value of

lipid	$p_{wat}(\%)$	a (Å)	w (Å)	x_b
monolinolein	34	85.8	6.2	0.55
monoolein	42	103.3	10.4	0.64
phytantriol	30	68.2	9.7	0.92
monovaccenin	48	128.2	12.3	0.57
monoolein	40	101	10.2	0.66
monolinolein	36	93.4	9.5	0.69
phytantriol	28	65.6	8.4	0.89

TABLE I. Estimation of the thickness of the region containing bound water for various systems. Data were taken from Refs.^{28,56}.

x_b for any system with known composition and structural parameters:

$$x_b = \frac{2A_0 \frac{l+w}{a} + \frac{4}{3}\pi\chi \left(\frac{l+w}{a}\right)^3 - (1 - \phi_{wat})}{\phi_{wat}}. \quad (22)$$

By using the results in Fig.7 top together with Eq.(20), one can thus estimate the value of D/D_0 for a hydrophilic particle diffusing in the IBCP under inspection. For our purposes, the heterogeneity of water mobility does not qualitatively change the conclusions reached in the present study, although being important for the quantitative details.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have conducted a systematic theoretical study on the transport properties of Inverse Bicontinuous Cubic Phases for the three common cases identified by the $\text{Im}\bar{3}m$, $\text{Pn}\bar{3}m$ and $\text{Ia}\bar{3}d$ symmetries. The conclusions that can be reached from our results are twofold. On the one hand, when inhomogeneities are not relevant the transport is entirely determined by the size of the diffusion domain normalized by the average Gaussian curvature of the minimal surface, thus leading to universal behavior. On the other hand, for highly confined molecules the presence and extent of bottlenecks become the main players, with $\text{Im}\bar{3}m$ and $\text{Ia}\bar{3}d$ showing the worst and best performances, respectively. A comparison with experimental data enables the estimation of the amount of water bound to the lipid heads, in good agreement with direct observations. In view of our results, the experimentally-observed fast diffusion of hydrophilic molecules within $\text{Im}\bar{3}m$ phases can be conclusively ascribed to the large amount of water available in real IBCPs with this symmetry, which overcomes the damping effects introduced by the

large amount of geometrical constrictions. Our findings indicate that the best strategy to increase transport would be to obtain $\text{Pn}\bar{3}m$ or $\text{Ia}\bar{3}d$ cubic phases with large water content, thus providing a useful guide to optimally devise related biotechnological applications.

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APPENDIX: METHODS

In our simulations, we considered the diffusion of hydrophilic particles inside the water channels as well as that of hydrophobic molecules within the lipid bilayer. We assumed that a particle cannot cross the boundary provided by the lipid heads. The diffusive motion was simulated according to Brownian Dynamics (BD) combined with Monte Carlo (MC) moves. Specifically, the usual BD updating rule was considered:

$$\begin{cases} x(t+dt) = x(t) + \sqrt{2D_0 dt} \zeta_x \\ y(t+dt) = y(t) + \sqrt{2D_0 dt} \zeta_y \\ z(t+dt) = z(t) + \sqrt{2D_0 dt} \zeta_z \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{r} \equiv (x, y, z)$ is the position vector of the particle; t the time; $dt = 10^{-4}$ the BD timestep; $D_0 = 0.01$ the diffusion coefficient of the particle in the absence of obstacles; and the stochastic numbers $\zeta_x, \zeta_y, \zeta_z$ are extracted from a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and unit variance. The definition of the time unit follows from our choice of $D_0 = 0.01$ and lattice parameter $a = 1$. The MC step consists in evaluating whether the new position has crossed the boundary imposed by the surface of the lipid bilayer: If this is the case, the move is rejected, otherwise it is accepted. To achieve a better accuracy, the MC time was rescaled by the acceptance ratio⁴⁷.

For a given value of l and assuming point particles (note that the finite size of a particle can be included by suitably correcting the value of l), the boundary surfaces are identified as the set of points having a distance from the minimal surface equal to l . For each IBCP, the corresponding TPMS can be accurately approximated as a nodal surface⁴⁸. Specifically, a minimal surface with lattice parameter a is defined by the equation $f(x, y, z) = 0$, where

$$f(x, y, z) = \begin{cases} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{a}\right) + \cos\left(\frac{2\pi y}{a}\right) + \cos\left(\frac{2\pi z}{a}\right) & \text{Im}\bar{3}m \\ \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi y}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{a}\right) + \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi z}{a}\right) & \text{Pn}\bar{3}m \\ \sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi y}{a}\right) + \sin\left(\frac{2\pi y}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi z}{a}\right) + \sin\left(\frac{2\pi z}{a}\right) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{a}\right) & \text{Ia}\bar{3}d \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

In order to identify the surface of the lipid bilayer for any value of l , we considered a $400 \times 400 \times 400$ grid encompassing a unit cell for a lattice parameter $a = 1$, and for each grid point we computed the distance from the minimal surface. In this way, by linear interpolation we could fastly estimate the distance of any given point from the surface. For each grid point A , the distance d_A was estimated by the bisection method. Noting that $0 \leq d_A < a = 1$, we fixed two boundary values $d_{down} = 0$ and $d_{up} = 1$, so that $d_{down} \leq d_A < d_{up}$. Then, we considered their mean $d_{try} = (d_{down} + d_{up})/2$ as a trial value and evaluated whether it was larger or smaller than d_A . To this aim, we sampled 10^6 random points of the spherical surface centered in A and having radius d_{try} . For each random point, we computed the sign of the formula identifying the nodal surface: If at least one point presents a sign inversion when compared to the same equation evaluated in A , the spherical surface intersects the minimal surface, therefore $d_{try} > d_A$. If no sign inversion is found, $d_{try} < d_A$. We then assigned $d_{up} = d_{try}$ in the former case, and $d_{down} = d_{try}$ in the latter. This resulted in narrowing down the range in which d_A is found. We iterated the algorithm until $d_{up} - d_{down} \leq 10^{-4}$. In this way, the final value $d_A \equiv (d_{down} + d_{up})/2$ gives an estimation of the real distance separating A from the TPMS with an error equal at most to $0.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

For the simulations based on Constant-Mean Curvature boundaries, we considered the approximations provided by the level surfaces defined by $f(x, y, z) = c^{61}$. Tuning the value of c enables the construction of surfaces with different values of mean curvature H (Fig.8). Within this approximation, we defined the diffusion domains as the sets of points satisfying $f(x, y, z) > c$. The MC step was suitably adapted to the present context, and simply consisted in checking the value of the function $f(x, y, z)$ and discarding the move if the condition defining the domain was not fulfilled.

Thanks to the scale-free nature of IBCPs⁶², the results obtained with a given lattice parameter a can be easily remapped to IBCPs with units having different size. Therefore, we considered only cubic phases with lattice parameter $a = 1$. Each point reported in the results section was computed as the statistical average of 10^5 independent realizations.

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FIG. 8. Mean curvature H normalized by the inverse of the lattice parameter, as a function of the parameter c defining the level set of the nodal approximations to CMC surfaces.

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